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ABSTRACT

Microstructured hollow-core fibers enable a flexible integration of high-power ultrafast lasers, offering the advantages of fiber-based beam delivery to ultrafast laser applications. For widespread industrial utilization of this technology, ever-increasing demands need to be fulfilled by adapting the beam delivery to new laser systems and process parameters. We demonstrate, for the first time ever, fiber-based beam delivery of high-power picosecond pulses with high polarization contrast in combination with direct laser interference patterning. By using an ultrashort pulse, high-power, near-infrared laser emitting a fundamental wavelength 1064 nm and pulse energy of 175 μ J at repetition rates up to 500 kHz, an interference pattern with a spatial period of 3.8 μ m is produced and applied in stainless steel, illustrating the proof of principle. The fiber-based delivery system represents a versatile tool for 3D microtexturing processes using ultrashort pulse laser systems. The demonstrated results pave the way for high-quality microstructuring of large surface areas by employing fiber-based beam delivery systems.

Key words: optical fibers, beam delivery, direct Laser interference patterning, polarization, laser surface structuring, laser microprocessing

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I. INTRODUCTION

Laser material processing encompasses critical industrial applications such as cutting and welding for various fields of applications within the aviation and automotive industry.¹ Macro processing such as laser cutting and welding provides precise, high-speed, and efficient methods for shaping various materials from metals to composites.² It offers unparalleled accuracy and minimal thermal distortion, which is crucial for producing complex geometries and high-quality finishes in 2D and 3D. The introduction of fiber-based beam delivery for high-power continuous wave (cw) lasers in the 1990s facilitated the widespread adoption of high-power lasers in industrial manufacturing.³ Optical fibers provide significant advantages in terms of flexibility, precision, and efficiency. They enable the transmission of high-power

laser beams over long distances with minimal loss, making them ideal for applications with multi-axis tool paths and in confined or hard-to-reach spaces. This capability is particularly beneficial in complex manufacturing environments where maneuverability and precision are paramount.

Beyond high-power cw laser applications, ultrafast lasers enable different processes, e.g., laser microprocessing which shows a wide array of applications across various industries, including aviation and the automotive sector. In addition to direct laser writing (DLW), direct laser interference patterning (DLIP) demonstrates numerous application fields using ultrashort pulses for creating easy-to-clean surfaces or anti-icing capabilities^{4–6} on different materials. Furthermore, DLIP enables the creation of several surface features simultaneously leading to a processing speed advantage with texturing rates up to 1.1 m²/min.⁷ These applications are not confined to

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just two-dimensional (2D) structures but extend to more complex 2.5D and even three-dimensional (3D) configurations.

Laser microprocessing applications can greatly benefit from fiber-based beam delivery systems. However, conventional solid-core optical fibers fail at single mode transmission of high-power ultrashort pulses due to the inherent laser induced damage threshold of the fiber material.^{3,8} In addition, the nonlinear refractive index of the solid fiber core can lead to nonlinear effects at peak powers below the damage threshold, substantially altering the properties of the delivered laser pulses. Microstructured hollow-core fibers offer a technological solution to these limitations. Here, the beam is guided inside a hollow core surrounded by a microstructured cladding. Most of the optical power is confined to the hollow core, effectively reducing the energy density at the glass structure. This leads to substantially increased effective damage thresholds and vastly reduced nonlinear effects. This can be further enhanced by evacuating the hollow core. The first industrial beam delivery system for ultrashort pulse lasers was introduced as early as 2015,⁹ utilizing the advantages of microstructured hollow-core fibers.

Recent research in hollow-core fiber technology aims at extending available wavelength ranges, reducing propagation losses, increasing power handling capabilities, and enhancing polarization maintaining properties.^{10–17} Polarization variations of the delivered pulses can affect the outcome of a multitude of laser micromachining processes, including techniques such as DLW and DLIP. For instance, the polarization influences the orientation of laser induced periodic surface structures (LIPSS) within DLIP fringes.¹⁸ Especially with large surface areas and complex parts, changes in the polarization when using nonpolarization maintaining fibers can lead to altering surface results at different locations on the workpiece. Here, a suitable combination of polarization maintaining properties and power handling capabilities is essential for successful process integration with reliable results in an industrial environment.

Within this work, we address the demand for flexible beam delivery systems in laser micromachining applications. We demonstrate a fiber-based beam delivery system capable of delivering high-power ultrashort pulses while maintaining a high polarization contrast. In a proof-of-principle experiment, we combined the fiber delivered pulses with two optical heads to apply a periodic pattern on a metallic surface by direct laser interference patterning.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Two different laser systems were used for the experiments. For characterization measurements at low-to-moderate average power, a custom fiber-based laser system, providing linearly polarized picosecond to subpicosecond pulses at a central wavelength of 1030 nm with 1 MHz repetition rate and up to 4 W average power (Amplitude) was employed.

For high-power characterization measurements and DLIP experiments, a customized InnoSlab-based laser system, emitting linearly polarized pulses with a duration of 12 ps at a central wavelength of 1064 nm, was used (Edgewave). The laser system was used at repetition rates of 100 and 500 kHz, providing an average power of 17.5 and 84.4 W, respectively, and pulse energies up to 175 μ J.

FIG. 1. Overview of an ultrafast beam delivery system consisting of a beam launching system (BLS), a laser light cable (LLK-UKP), and a modular processing head (MPH).

A. Fiber beam delivery system for ultrashort pulses

A typical ultrafast beam delivery system (Fig. 1) consists of a beam launching system (BLS) to couple the laser beam into the hollow-core fiber, a laser light cable (LLK-UKP), protecting the packaged fiber, and a modular processing head (MPH), shaping and guiding the beam to the work piece.

Coupling of high-power ultrashort pulses into hollow-core fibers requires precise matching of the free-space mode at the fiber entrance with the guided modes of the hollow-core fiber. The theoretical coupling efficiency is maximized for a beam-core ratio of $w/a \sim 0.7$, where a is the fiber core radius and w is the $1/e^2$ free-space beam waist size at the fiber entrance.¹⁹ To achieve optimal coupling conditions at the fiber entrance, a BLS (PT Photonic Tools GmbH) was employed. This enables the precise control of the beam waist location and beam size at the fiber entrance as well as the orientation of the input polarization relative to the slow axis of the laser light cable comprising the hollow-core fiber (Fig. 2).

The variable optics of the beam launching system allow for a wide adaptation to different laser systems and can be adjusted to accommodate for input beam diameters ($1/e^2$) of 1.5–5 mm. In addition, the beam launching system is equipped with sensors to detect positional and angular changes of the input beam. Fast actuated mirrors controlled via an active feedback loop compensate for drifts of the laser during long-term operation and laser power ramp up.

A birefringent antiresonant hollow-core fiber was selected, which offered an excellent compromise between power handling capabilities and polarization properties of the delivered pulses. For the proof-of-principle experiment, a 3.3 m long section of the antiresonant hollow-core fiber was packaged in a laser light cable (LLK-UKP, PT Photonic Tools GmbH) suitable for high-power operation in industrial environments. The hollow-core fiber connector has a fixed reference position for the fiber, which enables the exchange of laser light cables within minutes.

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FIG. 2. Ultrafast laser light cable connector with connections for water cooling, evacuation, safety circuits of the fiber continuity monitoring system, and integrated stray light and temperature sensors. Adapted from Ref. 20.

Furthermore, this reference point serves as a well-defined tool center point at the output of the laser light cable, enabling quick tool exchange for ultrafast applications. The connectors of the laser light cable (Fig. 2) are equipped with connections for water cooling to allow for proper thermal management and handle absorbed residual laser power that is not guided by the fiber.

Electronic safety circuitry, according to high-power industry standards, are included as well. At MW-level peak powers, nonlinear interaction between the ultrashort pulses and gas inside the hollow-core can lead to nonlinear effects such as self-focusing, self-phase modulation, and spectral broadening. While this can be utilized in other instances, e.g., for pulse compression and frequency conversion,^{3,21,22} nonlinear effects are mostly undesirable in the context of beam delivery. To severely reduce nonlinear interaction between high-power ultrashort pulses and the gas inside the hollow core, the laser light cable can be evacuated down to a few mbar, effectively lowering the nonlinear refractive index in the core by two orders of magnitude compared to atmospheric pressure. The mechanical design of the connector as well as the protective conduit are field proven from the high-power cw applications and allow for 24/7 robotic applications in an industrial environment.

The output of the laser light cable is connected to a modular processing head (PT Photonic Tools GmbH) which guides the laser beam from the fiber output to the work piece. An optical module with a focal length of $f = 75$ mm was chosen to collimate the beam exiting the laser light cable. The modular processing head is equipped with an imaging and camera module to monitor the output beam profile of the laser light cable during processing for easy optimization and quality control.

B. Direct laser interference patterning system

To obtain the interference pattern, the laser beam exiting the collimation module was split into two sub-beams using a DLIP optical head (Fraunhofer IWS/TU Dresden), obtaining a linelike

surface geometry. This setup enables the possibility to control the angle under which the two sub-beams superimpose on the surface. A detailed description of the optical setup can be found in Ref. 23. In addition, the ELIPSYS® DLIP head (SurFunction GmbH) was employed for extended analysis of the fiber delivered DLIP generation. The head contains an alternative approach of generating a linelike pattern, leading to the formation of a noncircular beam spot geometry on the material surface. Moreover, the shape of the emitted beam is changed using cylindrical lenses, containing the two-beam interference pattern. The optical setup permitted to focus the laser sub-beams to a working area with a dimension of $80\ \mu\text{m}$ in the X direction and $2.6\ \text{mm}$ in the Y-direction.

C. Topographical analysis

For investigating the surface topographies of the patterned samples, confocal microscopy (Sensofar S-Neox) was applied. The structure height of the patterns was measured by using the step height definition, representing the standard type A1 in the norm ISO5436-1. Furthermore, for measuring the structure depth of the induced LIPSS, atomic force microscopy (CoreAFM, Nanosurf) was utilized.

III. RESULTS

A. Industrial fiber beam delivery

The beam quality and transmission performance of the fiber-based beam delivery system was initially evaluated with the femtosecond laser system. Near-infrared pulses were coupled into the hollow-core fiber packaged inside the laser light cable. An adjustable wave plate, included in the BLS, was used to fine tune the polarization axis of the input beam to the slow axis of the laser light cable. The beam waist size w , waist location z , and lateral waist position x, y at the fiber entrance were optimized via a precisely adjustable lens system to match the mode field of the hollow-core fiber and maximize the transmission through the laser light cable. A transmission of up to $T_{\text{LLK}} \sim 77\%$ was achieved through the laser light cable.

The near-field beam profiles of the input and output beam were recorded with a beam analysis tool (PT Photonic Tools GmbH). This is a dedicated tool that can be attached to the BLS and the LLK-UKP to enable easy beam quality analysis of the input and output beam of the laser light cable in the field. It allows for a magnified image of the laser focus area under low and high-power operation. The recorded near-field beam profiles (Fig. 3) show excellent agreement with a zero order Hermite-gaussian fit, confirming the beam quality with near single mode operation. The near-field beam diameter ($1/e^2$) at the fiber exit was measured at $20.6\ \mu\text{m}$, in good agreement with the mode field diameter of the hollow-core fiber.

To characterize the polarization properties of the delivered laser pulses, the output of the laser light cable is collimated and passed through a broadband polarizing beamsplitter onto a power detector. The polarization extinction ratio (PER) is calculated as

$$\text{PER} = 10 \log_{10}(P_{\text{max}}/P_{\text{min}}), \quad (1)$$

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FIG. 3. Near-field beam profile before (a) and after (b) propagation through the LLK-UKP at 1030 nm, 1 MHz measured with the beam analysis tool.

where P_{\max} and P_{\min} are the maximum and minimum transmitted power levels measured with orthogonal orientations of the polarizing beam splitter. The polarization extinction ratio of the linearly polarized input beam was measured in a similar manner directly before the beam launching system. The measured PER of the linearly polarized input beam before the BLS exceeded 28 dB. The polarization extinction ratio at the fiber exit was measured at 21.3 ± 1.5 dB when the laser light cable was routed as specified.

To evaluate the effect of mechanical stress on the beam properties during dynamic operation, the polarization extinction ratio of the delivered pulses and the transmitted average power were measured for different bending radii of the laser light cable (see Fig. 4). Here, the minimum bending radius was limited to values above 100 mm due to the intended rigidity of the laser light cable, effectively protecting the packaged hollow-core fiber. The PER of the delivered laser pulses always exceeded 20 dB for bending radii $r > 200$ mm while the transmission through the laser light cable remained completely unaffected (see Fig. 4). Considering machine designs with typical minimum bending radii $r_{\min} > 250$ mm for

FIG. 4. Measured polarization extinction ratio and transmission of delivered laser pulses for varying bending radii of the laser light cable.

ultrafast fiber beam delivery applications, the demonstrated polarization and pulse energy properties of the delivered pulses confirm that the LLK-UKP is well suited for dynamic polarization sensitive laser micromachining applications.

B. Characterization of high-power picosecond pulse beam delivery

The fiber-based beam delivery system was combined with the described InnoSlab-based laser system to evaluate its performance at input pulse energies of up to $175 \mu\text{J}$ and to reach the optical fluences required for direct laser interference patterning on metals.

The repetition rate of the laser system was set to 100 kHz for an average power of up to 17.5 W and 500 kHz for a maximum average power up of to 84.4 W, with corresponding pulse energies of 175 and $169 \mu\text{J}$. The LLK-UKP was evacuated to pressures below 6 mbar to reduce undesirable interaction with residual gas and the connectors were water-cooled to establish a stable thermal condition. In this configuration, the LLK-UKP is capable of transmitting average powers well above 100 W.

The recorded near-field beam profiles before and after the laser light cable show excellent agreement with a zero order Hermite-gaussian fit (Fig. 5), indicating excellent beam quality throughout the power range.

The measured input and output pulse energies of the laser light cable are depicted in Fig. 6. A linear power dependency, without artificial influence from the LLK-UKP, is demonstrated with identical performance for 100 and 500 kHz, indicating that the average power has no influence on the transmission. An inspection of the LLK-UKP after the proof-of-principle test showed no damage to the fiber itself. The maximum occurring fluence F and peak power P_{peak} inside the hollow-core fiber are estimated from the recorded input pulse energy, the mode field beam diameter, and pulse duration as $F = 97.2 \text{ J}/\text{cm}^2$ and $P_{\text{peak}} = 13.5 \text{ MW}$, well above the limits of conventional single mode solid-core fibers.

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FIG. 5. Near-field beam profiles before (a) and after (b) propagation through the LLK-UKP at 1064 nm, 500 kHz, measured with the beam analysis tool at an average input power of 84.4 W.

FIG. 6. Measured output pulse energy vs input pulse energy of the laser light cable at 500 and 100 kHz repetition rate.

C. Direct laser interference patterning

Using the ELIPSYS® DLIP head, the optical analysis by a beam profiling camera reveals the desired periodical pattern in a linelike intensity distribution. The interference pattern leads to an altering intensity distribution between the interference maxima and minima as shown in Fig. 7.

The spatial period of the optical interference pattern was measured with $6.0\ \mu\text{m}$. Since the employed laser source depicts a maximum pulse energy of $175\ \mu\text{J}$, the resulting laser fluence after the ELIPSYS® DLIP head was not sufficient for ablating metal materials in this configuration. For surface texturing, the DLIP head from Fraunhofer IWS/TU Dresden was used,

FIG. 7. Intensity distribution recorded at the work piece location after the ELIPSYS® DLIP processing head, showing an interference pattern with a spatial period of $6\ \mu\text{m}$.

FIG. 8. Microscope image (a) of steel sample, structured with 100 kHz, 12 ps pulses. (b) Confocal measured 3D image of applied structure showing DLIP with a spatial period of $3.8\ \mu\text{m}$, an average structure depth of $1.2\ \mu\text{m}$. (c) AFM measurement of superimposed LIPSS on top of the DLIP fringes.

processing a stainless-steel plate with a mirrorlike surface finish. Here, the maximum pulse energy of the laser system was sufficient to ablate the material and form a linelike texture with a spatial period of $3.8\ \mu\text{m}$, as shown in Fig. 8. Next to the DLIP

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fringes, LIPSS are noticeable, inferring that the polarization state kept constant during transport through the fiber delivery, as illustrated in Figs. 8(a) and 8(c). This also holds true for cable movement during the process. The confocal measurement reveals an average structure depth of $1.2 \pm 0.15 \mu\text{m}$. In addition, the AFM analysis reveals an average structure depth of the LIPSS of $168 \pm 52 \text{ nm}$.

IV. SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

In this work, we demonstrated the feasibility of fiber-based beam delivery of high-power picosecond pulses with birefringent hollow-core fibers for laser micromachining processes such as direct laser interference patterning. For this purpose, $175 \mu\text{J}$ near-infrared picosecond pulses with a repetition rate up to 500 kHz and average power exceeding 84 W were launched into an antiresonant hollow-core fiber. In a first proof-of-principle experiment, the delivered picosecond pulses were utilized to apply an interference pattern with a spatial period of $3.8 \mu\text{m}$ in stainless steel via direct laser interference patterning with a structure depth of $1.2 \pm 0.15 \mu\text{m}$.

The demonstrated flexible fiber beam delivery paves the way toward using complex multi-axis manipulators and robotic arms for polarization sensitive applications with ultrashort high-power pulses. This enables industrial applications such as laser surface structuring of large and complex shaped parts as envisioned within the framework of the Horizon Europe project OPeriTIC.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Paul Froemel: Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Robert Baumann:** Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Andrés Fabián Lasagni:** Funding acquisition (equal); Project administration (equal); Resources (equal); Supervision (equal). **Sebastian Eilzer:** Funding acquisition (equal); Project administration (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – original draft (supporting); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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